

THE IMPORTANCE OF METHODOLOGY IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Esanova Maftuna Bakhadirova

Teacher Department of Languages Samarkand State Medical University

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ABSTRACT

Studying foreign languages is inseparable part of professional teaching of specialists in different fields. Successful problem solving and widening of contacts with international companies depends on the quality of language teaching. The success of teaching very often depends on the methodics of teaching foreign languages and on the ability of teachers to use different modern methodics to solve certain educational goals.

KEYWORDS: language education, descriptive, inductive, deductive, comparative, consequently, assessment techniques, language teaching

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in a natural environment, i.e. in the family, in the community or in an organized manner. Knowledge of language phenomena is taught theoretically. Knowledge of languages, especially multilingualism, is of great importance in our time of increased international relations. Pupils and students studying in our country usually study three languages. These languages are referred to by special names. These are: mother tongue, second language, and foreign language. The mother tongue is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. When talking about the second language, it is considered as the language of brothers and neighbors of other nationalities.

A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. By carefully mastering the achievements of the methodical science, the foreign language teacher will be able to clearly know the standard of language experience of the student and to improve it further. Effective teaching of foreign languages requires knowledge of its methodology. Learning and teaching foreign languages largely depends on the theoretical development of foreign language teaching methodology issues and the creative application of theory in practice.

The methodology of foreign language teaching as a science has more than 200 years of history. During this period, it can be observed that different attitudes towards foreign language teaching methodology were expressed. One of these views belongs to academician L.V. Shcherba. In his opinion, although the methodology of teaching any subject is a subject, it is not considered a

theoretical subject. It solves practical issues. In particular, the methodology of foreign language teaching does not rely only on psychological evidence, but is based on general and specific linguistic studies. If linguistics deals with the origin and laws of movement of language phenomena, the methodology answers the question of what should be done in order to use the necessary language phenomenon in practice based on these laws. The most valuable books on methodology are also written by linguists. These include G. Suit, one of the 19th century phoneticians and a great English linguist, O. Yesperson, who is considered the most original phonetician and theoretical linguist in England at the end of the 19th and early 20th centuries, and one of the most prominent French linguists in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, F. .Bryuns and Brealya, prominent anglicist and famous phonetician V. Fyotor and others. Academician L.V. Shcherba and his mentor, the great linguist scientist I.A. Baudouin-de-Courtone and their students dealt with the issue of language teaching methodology in Russia. Psychologists have a different attitude to the methodology of foreign language teaching. Professor V.A. Artemov made a valuable comment about the relationship between methodology and psychology. In his opinion, psychology provides material for methodology. Methodology studies how the teacher conducts the lesson. Psychology deals with how students learn this subject. However, this opinion cannot be fully agreed. Because the teacher in the process of teaching, and the student in the period of mastering, experience certain mental processes and states, whether they want to or not, they face and are influenced by the laws of psychology.

A deeper study of the literature on the history of methodology shows that some researchers call methodology an art. They usually refer to the idea of the French Methodist Penlache, that there are no "good" or "bad" methods, there are "good" or "bad" teachers. People who have such an opinion can be answered with the thoughts of the German Methodist E. Otto, expressed in 1924. He says: "If someone considers methodology to be an art, he confuses the theory of science with its practical application."

Each discipline has its own set of concepts. Among the main concepts adopted in the foreign language teaching methodology, the following can be included: educational system, educational method, educational principle, educational tool, methodical method.

Foreign language teaching method means a set of teacher and student activities that ensure achievement of practical, general educational, educational and developmental goals of foreign language teaching. The term method is used in

the sense of "set of educational methods" and "direction of education". First, in the theory of education, the process is used in the sense of methods, and in the second sense, we can find it in works on the history of teaching methods. For example, the translation method, the correct method, the conscious-comparative method, the traditional method, the intensive method, etc.

The application of methods in foreign language teaching has been around for a long time, and principles are relatively new methodological terms. Historically, the methods were grouped into four groups, and their names were called "translation", "correct", "comparative", "mixed".

The term intercultural communication is widely used in foreign language teaching methodology. It is this concept that we can apply in many different contexts. In fact: Intercultural communication is communication-information about the social origin, mentality, national character, way of life, customs, value system, etc. of representatives of different cultures. In this process, it is necessary to educate and develop students in the spirit of respect, patience and correct understanding of the culture of the country they are studying.

Every foreign language lesson is a cultural intersection, a practice of intercultural communication. Because every foreign language word in this process reflects foreign life and culture. The task before teachers is to develop the ability of pupils and students to communicate. For this, it is necessary to learn new methods of education aimed at developing the four speech activities in a foreign language, teaching manuals that teach people to communicate effectively.

The formula of intercultural communication is patience and tolerance. It is necessary to avoid socio-cultural mistakes in intercultural communication. For example, in German people, "Tee oder Kaffee?" that is, we answer the question "tea or coffee" in our native language with "Tee", "tea", but in German, such an answer is not appropriate. In German, the answer is "Bitte, Tee", that is, "Thank you, tea". Words connect people through communication. As a result of using the new material simultaneously in all types of speech activity skills and abilities are created. In this process, the quality and effectiveness of education will increase if communication tools, demonstration, types of modern technology, methods, and the principle of consistency are provided.

A person begins to acquire communication skills from infancy. Communication is an important condition for socialization of a person. At this point, it is necessary to know what pedagogical communication actually is.

Pedagogical communication is a mutual cooperation between a teacher and a student, which is based on the exchange of information, first of all educational information, helps to understand the partner of pedagogical communication, as well as to implement mutual cooperation activities. In this case, information is conveyed both verbally, that is, through speech, and non-verbally - through means. In the process of pedagogical communication, the teacher should play the main role and be an example for students. This is evaluated by his communicative culture.

The teacher's communicative culture can include the following:

1. Communication skills.
2. Educator's openness to communication.
3. Communication culture of the teacher.
4. Pedagogical communication methods.

CONCLUSION

Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted discipline, in which a person undergoes complex psychological changes. In particular, the process of comparing the native language with a foreign language occurs. Various teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, teaching by comparing the foreign language with the mother tongue gives an effective result. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology.

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